

Physiological responses to low CO₂ over prolonged drought as primers for forest-grassland transitions

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Running title

Drought and CO₂ effects in savanna trees and grass

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Abstract

Savannas dominated by grasses with scattered C₃ trees expanded between 24 and 9 million years ago in low latitudes at the expense of forests. Fire, herbivory, the susceptibility of trees to declining atmospheric CO₂ concentrations (denoted [CO₂]_a), and drought are proposed as key drivers of this transition. The role of disturbance is well-studied, but physiological arguments are mostly derived from models and paleorecords, without direct experimental evidence. In replicated comparative experimental trials, we examined the physiological effects of [CO₂]_a and prolonged drought in a broad-leaf forest tree, a savanna tree, and a savanna C₄ grass. We show that the forest tree was more disadvantaged than either the savanna tree or C₄ grass by the low [CO₂]_a and increasing aridity. Our experiments provide new insights into the role of the intrinsic physiological susceptibility of trees in priming the disturbance-driven transition from forest to savanna in the conditions of the early Miocene.

Introduction

Savannas, open grasslands with scattered trees, occupy environments with climates that could support closed forests¹. Modern savannas are dominated by C₄ grasses², operating a biochemical CO₂ concentrating mechanism that forces CO₂ into the C₃ photosynthetic apparatus. Savannas are

32 maintained by periodic disturbance from a combination of fire, which is more important on nutri-
33 ent poor soils, and herbivory, which is more important on richer soils³⁻⁸. During the Miocene, be-
34 tween 24 and 9 million years ago, savannas expanded over closed, broad-leaf forests at low-lati-
35 tudes^{9,10}. Multiple proxies indicate a decrease of [CO₂]_a from 700~1000 ppm in the Oligocene to
36 ~200 ppm in the early Miocene^{11,12} and a concurrent increase in monsoon-driven seasonal arid-
37 ity¹³⁻¹⁵, which slowed tree growth, and reduced sapling recruitment via increased mortality^{4,13,14},
38 exacerbated by large herbivores¹⁶. In contrast, elevated [CO₂]_a can favour C₃ over C₄ species¹⁷,
39 and mitigate stress¹⁸, but water limitations may dampen CO₂ fertilization gains^{19,20}. While dis-
40 turbance by large herbivores is well-studied, few studies have addressed the interactive physio-
41 logical effects of [CO₂]_a and water availability, with current ideas based on theory and process-
42 based ecosystem models²¹⁻²³. Insights from C₃ and C₄ forb acclimation to low [CO₂]_a highlight
43 the crucial of these interactions for understanding how the Earth's vegetation responded to past
44 changes in [CO₂]_a¹⁸, but direct comparative experimental evidence for tree and grass responses to
45 variations in [CO₂]_a and drought is lacking.

46 Here we investigate the physiological responses of present-day savanna and forest species to
47 concurrent variations in [CO₂]_a and water availability. We hypothesized that: (H₁) decreasing
48 [CO₂]_a would reduce CO₂ assimilation rates more in C₃ trees than in C₄ grasses during drought
49 and increase water loss from leaves, amplifying drought effects; (H₂) because savanna trees
50 evolved under declining [CO₂]_a and increasing aridity, they would be less disadvantaged than for-
51 est trees by sub-ambient [CO₂]_a under prolonged drought; and (H₃) because starch is the main re-
52 serve for resprouting, the capacity of trees and grasses to recover from drought depends upon the
53 content of starch in leaves and roots.

54 To evaluate our three physiology-based savanna evolution hypotheses, we undertook repli-
55 cated comparative experimental trials across three species of representative contrasting functional
56 types: *Celtis africana* [N.L.Burm.], a deciduous broad-leaf forest tree common in southern Africa
57 that represents plants of the fire-sensitive forests and woodlands that dominated before C₄ grassy
58 savanna expansion⁹; *Vachellia karroo* [Hayne] (*Acacia*), a nitrogen-fixing tree, typical of open
59 savannas; and *Eragrostis curvula* [(Schrad.) Nees], a drought-tolerant C₄ grass common to fre-
60 quently burned or grazed mesic savannas^{4,24}. The plants were grown in replicated controlled-en-
61 vironments under 200, 400 or 800 ppm [CO₂]_a and a controlled drought was imposed over five
62 months by reducing watering in four steps from 80% to 30% of gravimetrically determined pot
63 capacity, followed by a month-long re-watering back to 80%. We characterised canopy transpira-
64 tion, leaf gas exchange, photosynthetic physiology and starch content at all [CO₂]_a-watering level
65 combinations, providing a detailed description of the physiological responses of savanna species
66 to the range of [CO₂]_a expected for past, current, and future scenarios.

Results

We combined the response of individual species to drought and re-watering across the $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ levels with an inter-species comparison of responses to $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ over a season-long drought. As expected, all species reacted to drought by decreasing photosynthesis and transpiration, but the timing of the response and the plants' ability to recover differed between species. Over prolonged drought, low growth $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ was more detrimental for the trees than the C_4 grass, with the forest tree *C. africana* suffering worse than the savanna tree *V. karroo*.

Plant water use and leaf water status

In the trees, gravimetrically determined canopy evapotranspiration (E_{plant}) was independent of growth $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ at all watering levels (Figure 1; see Table S1 for *P*-values and details of the statistical analysis). In the grass, E_{plant} was higher at 200 ppm (sub-ambient') than at 800 ppm ('elevated') $[\text{CO}_2]_a$, both under well-watered and drought conditions (Figure 1). All species responded to drought with an immediate decline in E_{plant} , which was steeper in the savanna species *V. karroo* and *E. curvula* than in *C. africana*. Under well-watered conditions, leaf relative water content (RWC) consistently scaled with growth $[\text{CO}_2]_a$, but differences were small, and significant in *E. curvula* only. Drought resulted in an immediate decline in RWC in the savanna species; the reduction was delayed until 40 and 30% watering levels in *C. africana*, but, then, RWC dropped at markedly lower levels, especially at sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$.

For all species under well-watered conditions, midday water potential (Ψ_{leaf}) was significantly higher at elevated and ambient than at sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ (Figure 2). At the onset of drought significant reductions in Ψ_{leaf} and predawn leaf water potential (Ψ_{pd} , a proxy for soil water potential) occurred for savanna species at all $[\text{CO}_2]_a$, while the response was delayed until 50% watering in *C. africana*.

For most combinations of species and $[\text{CO}_2]_a$, re-watering recovered E_{plant} , RWC, Ψ_{leaf} and Ψ_{pd} to values similar or higher than those for well-watered plants, except for *C. africana* leaf RWC at elevated $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ and Ψ_{pd} at ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$; and in *E. curvula* Ψ_{pd} at all $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ and Ψ_{leaf} at ambient and elevated $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ (Figure 1 and 2).

Photosynthetic and stomatal responses

In the trees and under well-watered conditions, photosynthetic rate (A_{op}) was higher at elevated than at sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ but A_{op} was insensitive to $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ levels in well-watered *E. curvula* (Figure 3). The response of stomatal conductance (g_s) to $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ under well-watered conditions was similar in the savanna species *V. karroo* and *E. curvula*, progressively decreasing with

99 growth $[\text{CO}_2]_a$. In the savanna species A_{op} and g_s responded faster to drought than in *C. africana*,
100 with large decreases in A_{op} and g_s as soon as watering was reduced to 60%, especially at ambient
101 and sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$. After the initial drop, g_s stabilised in *E. curvula*, but continued to de-
102 crease in *V. karroo*. In contrast, *C. africana*, had a gradual reduction in A_{op} that only became sig-
103 nificant at 50%, 40% and 30% watering for high, ambient and sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$, respectively.
104 In *C. africana*, the response of g_s to drought was only significant at elevated $[\text{CO}_2]_a$. Re-watering
105 led to recovery of A_{op} and g_s to initial levels in all species and $[\text{CO}_2]_a$, except for A_{op} in *C. afri-*
106 *cana* and g_s in *V. karroo*, which remained low at sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$.

107 *Photosynthetic capacity*

108 In *E. curvula*, all the photosynthetic parameters (R_{LIGHT} , $Y(\text{CO}_2)_{\text{LL}}$, GA_{sat} and LCP , Figure 4)
109 derived from A - $PPFD$ curves (Figure S3) were independent of growth $[\text{CO}_2]_a$. The trees grown at
110 elevated $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ had higher respiration in the light (R_{LIGHT}) and light saturated gross assimilation
111 rate (GA_{sat}) than at sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ (Figure 4). *V. karroo* grown at elevated $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ had higher
112 initial quantum yield for CO_2 fixation ($Y(\text{CO}_2)_{\text{LL}}$) for all watering levels.

113 All species responded to drought with a concerted downregulation of photosynthetic parame-
114 ters. However, only *C. africana* reduced R_{LIGHT} and was able to maintain constant $Y(\text{CO}_2)_{\text{LL}}$ de-
115 spite drought, resulting in a progressive reduction in the light compensation point (LCP) as
116 drought progressed. In contrast, drought decreased $Y(\text{CO}_2)_{\text{LL}}$ in *E. curvula*, which negatively im-
117 pinged on the LCP . In all species and $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ levels, GA_{SAT} decreased with drought. The steepest
118 decrease was for *V. karroo*, which, at 40% watering, reduced GA_{SAT} to an average across $[\text{CO}_2]_a$
119 levels of 12% of the initial values, compared to 44% and 53% for *E. curvula* and *C. africana*, re-
120 spectively.

121 In *C. africana*, all the photosynthetic parameters (CE , V_{cmax} , Γ , and A_{sat} , Figure 5 and S4) de-
122 rived from A - C_i curves measured under a $PPFD$ of $1500 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, were independent of
123 growth $[\text{CO}_2]_a$. *V. karroo* had higher carboxylation efficiency (CE) and CO_2 saturated assimi-
124 lation rate (A_{sat}) when grown at elevated $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ (Figure 5). In *E. curvula*, CE and maximal PEP
125 carboxylation rate (V_{pmax}) were lower in plants grown under elevated than sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$. *E.*
126 *curvula* sharply reduced the CO_2 compensation point (Γ) in response to drought under elevated
127 $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ but not under any other $[\text{CO}_2]_a$. In the two savanna species, and at all $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ levels, CE
128 decreased with drought. Maximal carboxylation rates for rubisco (V_{CMAX}) and PEP (V_{PMAX}) de-
129 creased in all species and $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ levels, to values that, at 40% watering, were 25%, 39%, and
130 46% of the initial values in *V. karroo*, *C. africana*, and *E. curvula*, respectively. A_{SAT} followed
131 the same decreasing trend and promptly declined at 60% watering in *V. karroo* all $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ levels,

132 while significant differences were delayed until 50% watering in the other two species. Γ in-
133 creased with drought only in *V. karroo*. The response of the photochemical integrity of photosys-
134 tem II as indicated by F_v/F_m is shown in Supporting Information Figure S6. *E. curvula* main-
135 tained F_v/F_m throughout the experiment, while F_v/F_m followed the general trend of A_{op} in the
136 trees: dropping at drought onset in *V. karroo* and later in *C. africana*.

137 Re-watering resulted in recovery of all photosynthetic parameters to initial levels in *V. karroo*,
138 and in all parameters except $Y(\text{CO}_2)_{LL}$ and LCP in *E. curvula*. However, in *C. africana*, R_{LIGHT} ,
139 G_{ASAT} , LCP , and V_{CMAX} , did not recover (Figure 4 and 5).

140 *Leaf and root starch content*

141 In *E. curvula* starch content in both leaves and roots was independent of growth $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ (Fig-
142 ure 6). In *V. karroo*, root starch content was not affected by growth $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ but leaf starch content
143 decreased faster in response to drought in plants grown under sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ than at any
144 other $[\text{CO}_2]_a$. *C. africana* under elevated $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ had higher starch content both in roots and leaves
145 compared with plants grown under sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ for most watering levels.

146 In the trees, leaf starch content decreased rapidly with drought in *V. karroo* (significant de-
147 creases occurred at 60–50% watering) and gradually in *C. africana* (significant effects delayed
148 until 30% watering). Conversely, in the C_4 grass *E. curvula*, leaf starch content did not decrease
149 with drought. In the savanna tree and grass, leaf starch content increased at lower watering levels
150 at sub-ambient and ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$.

151 Root starch content slowly decreased with drought in *V. karroo*, but it was independent of wa-
152 tering in the other species. After re-watering, leaf starch content recovered to initial values in the
153 trees, but it became significantly lower than at any other period in the grass. Root starch remained
154 low in *V. karroo*.

155 *Effect of $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ over prolonged drought*

156 To compare the effect of growth $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ over a season-long drought across species, we com-
157 puted the difference between the natural logarithm of values at either sub- or elevated- $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ and
158 those at ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ for each variable. The change in natural logarithms of variables is inde-
159 pendent of the initial value and unit of the variable, and therefore allows for direct comparison
160 across species (see Table 1 caption for more details). We tested if the response differed between
161 trees and the C_4 grass (H_1) or between the two trees (H_2).

162 Growth at sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ decreased g_s , A_{op} , GA_{sat} , and leaf starch more in trees than in the
163 grass and decreased Γ more in the grass than in the trees (Table 1). Comparing the savanna spe-
164 cies, sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ decreased all photosynthetic indicators more in the savanna tree, *V. kar-*
165 *roo*, than in the savanna grass, *E. curvula*. The trees responded to sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ by decreas-
166 ing A_{op} and LCP more in *C. africana* than *V. karroo*. Interestingly, this was accompanied by a
167 larger decrease in g_s in *V. karroo* than in *C. africana*, indicating higher non-stomatal limitation in
168 *C. africana*. The response to elevated $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ was similar between trees and the grass, but A_{op} and
169 GA_{sat} increased more in *V. karroo* than in *C. africana* and *E. curvula*.

170 Discussion

171 Our experimental design combined three $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ levels spanning the likely range of values ex-
172 pected for past and future scenarios (200, 400 and 800 ppm) with a gradual stepped reduction in
173 water supply (80% to 30% of pot capacity) followed by re-watering. This allowed for the investi-
174 gation of the physiological responses of acclimation with unprecedented temporal resolution,
175 avoiding confounding effects of rapid senescence that occur when plants are deliberately killed in
176 irrigation suspension experiments²⁷.

177 Our first hypothesis (H_1) stated that during a prolonged drought, sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ would
178 reduce assimilation more in trees than in grasses, and this was supported by the experiment evi-
179 dence: sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ reduced A_{op} and GA_{sat} more in trees than in the C_4 grass *E. curvula*;
180 however, contrary to what we thought, over the course of drought, sub-ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ increased
181 g_s more in *E. curvula* than in the trees (Table 1). The response to drought was found to be time-
182 dependent. In C_4 grasses short-term dips in leaf water potential between days²⁸ or around midday
183 ²⁹ cause rapid declines in assimilation that are mainly due to non-stomatal limitation³⁰. Here we
184 found that, after an initial reduction, *E. curvula* stabilised A_{op} and g_s while photosynthesis contin-
185 ued to decline in the trees. We reason that *E. curvula* may take days to acclimate to drought;
186 when water potential falls fast, non-stomatal limitations would reduce assimilation to the point
187 where avoidance becomes advantageous. Indeed, from 60% watering, *E. curvula* rolled its leaves
188 in the evening of the day after watering, and increasingly earlier at lower watering levels, then
189 promptly unfurled after watering. In contrast, the trees started dropping their leaves at 50% water-
190 ing, and by 30% watering they were almost completely defoliated.

191 Both leaf shedding and rolling effectively reduce canopy evapotranspiration, conferring pro-
192 tection against hydraulic damage³¹. While leaf shedding is ubiquitous, rolling is more common in
193 spontaneous and cultivated grasses and cereals³²⁻³⁴. Rolled leaves remain *in situ* meaning essen-
194 tial resources (nitrogen, phosphorous) are retained in live tissue rather than relocated or lost
195 through leaf senescence. Unfurling operates over hourly timescales, allowing rapid exploitation

196 of post- or mid-drought soil water pulses. Conversely, recovery after leaf shedding requires grow-
197 ing new leaves, imposing a lag time of weeks or months. Redmann³⁵ proposed that rolling am-
198 phistomatous leaves would be selected for in habitats where diurnal water supply and demand
199 fluctuate widely. These mechanisms explained a rapid 90% increase in assimilation in a C₄ sa-
200 vanna grass following a mid-drought rainfall event compared with only 22–26% increase in oak
201 trees³⁶, conferring C₄ grasses a growth advantage over trees relying on regrowth³¹. This ad-
202 vantage would be more pronounced under sub-ambient [CO₂]_a as the photorespiratory and evapo-
203 rative losses of C₃ trees accelerate senescence^{37,38}.

204 Our second hypothesis (H₂), that the savanna tree *V. karroo* would be less disadvantaged at
205 sub-ambient [CO₂]_a than the forest tree *C. africana*, was also supported by our experimental evi-
206 dence (Table 1). However, the timing of the response to drought differed between the trees. *V.*
207 *karroo* rapidly closed its stomata (Figure 3) – consistent with a previously described isohydric be-
208 haviour²⁶, reduced transpiration (Figure 1), dropped leaves, and accumulated starch (Figure 6).
209 Conversely, *C. africana* maintained both E_{plant} and leaves for longer (Figure 1 and 3), but at the
210 expense of marked leaf dehydration as drought intensified at sub-ambient [CO₂]_a (Figure 1).
211 Upon re-watering, *V. karroo* fully recovered A_{op} and photosynthetic potential. Whereas *C. afri-*
212 *cana* did not recover leaf RWC at elevated [CO₂]_a, A_{op} under sub-ambient [CO₂]_a (Figure 1 and
213 3), and only 4 out of the 8 photosynthetic parameters (GA_{SAT} , V_{CMAX} , R_{LIGHT} and LCP) (Figure 4
214 and 5), further supporting hypothesis H₂.

215 By delaying leaf senescence, *C. africana* may have traded its capacity to remobilise nutrients
216 from leaves to storage organs, and that this, in turn, affected its capacity to recover, particularly
217 under sub-ambient [CO₂]_a. *C. africana* maintained dehydrated leaves on the tree for some time
218 before shedding. Contrasting strategies of rapid versus delayed leaf shedding were also observed
219 in closely related savanna and forest eucalyptus species³⁹, potentially underpinned by the ad-
220 vantage of shading-out competitors^{21,40}. Further, *C. africana* reduced leaf respiration, which re-
221 sulted in maintaining quantum yield and in a substantial reduction of the light compensation point
222 (Figure 4). This is critical under low light⁴¹ because it helps saplings to maintain a net positive
223 carbon balance in the shady forest understory⁴². Overall, this adaptive shade strategy may be suc-
224 cessful during mild, short duration droughts⁶, but not for a longer period.

225 Our third hypotheses (H₃), that the capacity to recover from drought depends upon the content
226 of starch in roots and leaves, was not supported by our results, with recovery independent of the
227 starch content of both organs. However, we found that leaf starch content might be related to
228 drought resilience. In both *E. curvula* and *V. karroo* under sub-ambient [CO₂]_a, leaf starch con-
229 tent at 30% and 40% watering was significantly higher than at higher watering levels, but such an

230 increase was not observed in *C. africana* (Figure 6). This change in leaf starch content was ac-
231 companied by more negative Ψ in the savanna tree and grass than in the forest tree *C. africana*
232 (Figure 1). Starch hydrolysis may play a central role in cavitation repair and osmotic adjustment
233 following drought injury⁴³⁻⁴⁵. Thus, concentrating starch in leaves could have increased the opera-
234 tional safety margins against hydraulic failure for the savanna species under drought. Our obser-
235 vations are consistent with reports showing accumulation of non-structural carbohydrates in *V.*
236 *karroo* leaves under drought conditions²⁶. In montane grasslands under ambient $[\text{CO}_2]_a$, the pro-
237 portion of recent assimilate allocated to root storage increased during drought⁴⁶. In this view,
238 starch likely functioned as insurance against drought at the expense of growth, rather than a sink
239 for carbon overspill^{3,47-52}. Finally, our data do not support the suggestion that leaves under high
240 $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ accumulate starch to levels that inhibit photosynthetic performance¹⁸. Starch content in-
241 creased with $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ only within *C. africana* roots, but this was associated with an increase in A_{op} .

242 Physiological responses contribute to ecosystem shifts from forests to savannas and *vice versa*.
243 Our results show that forest trees were disadvantaged by low $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ and increasing aridity, con-
244 ditions that occurred during the early Miocene. Uncertainties in the lower bound of Miocene
245 $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ would likely affect the magnitude of plant responses and across a lower gradient in
246 $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ the magnitude of treatment effects could be diminished⁵³. Trees carry a carbon tax on
247 large woody structures, both structural and for maintenance, which is avoided by herbaceous
248 grasses. Low $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ and drought could result in death of branches and trees through carbon star-
249 vation or hydraulic failure, but generally these occur under exceptional levels of stress⁵⁴. It was
250 shown that drought and low $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ were not sufficient by itself to tip the transitional balance to
251 open ecosystems⁵⁵, but would likely increase the intrinsic susceptibility of trees to the effects of
252 disturbance. This may have played a role in the expansion of grassy savannas at the expense of
253 forests under low atmospheric CO_2 concentrations⁹ some 20 million year ago¹. Under low $[\text{CO}_2]_a$
254 trees grow slower and allocate less biomass both to physical (thorns)⁵⁶ and chemical defences³⁸,
255 accelerating canopy opening by browsers⁵⁷. While forest grasses seldom produce enough biomass
256 to burn, opening environments would accumulate more grass biomass, fuelling deeper penetra-
257 tion of fires. The competition for water and nutrients would intensify and slow-growing trees
258 would be less likely to grow tall enough to escape destruction by fire (escaping the ‘fire trap’).
259 This, in turn, would reduce sapling recruitment to mature trees⁵⁸, conditioning the ecosystems to
260 entrain positive feedbacks involving fires². It has been suggested that during early stages of for-
261 est-grassland transition, local factors including soil properties, rainfall intensity, and topography,
262 were critical in shaping the competition between grasses and tree saplings^{5,59-63}. In these opening
263 habitats, quick-responding trees like *V. karroo* would progressively displace forest trees such as

264 *C. africana*. The shift in the proportion of C₃ and C₄ grasses could have been driven by con-
265 trasting responses of C₃ and C₄ grasses to drought⁶⁴, ultimately giving these emerging ecosystems
266 the shape of modern savannas. Differences in the timing of the response²⁸ suggest that C₄ grasses
267 evolved different mechanisms of avoidance and tolerance to drought than C₃ grasses (in addition
268 to those described above, faster responding stomata⁶⁵, enhanced water delivery to leaves^{28,66}, and
269 low stomatal conductance⁶⁷).

270 Similar interactions between physiology and disturbance may operate at increasing [CO₂]_a.
271 Ecosystem models predict that elevated [CO₂]_a will shift areas that could currently support multi-
272 ple stable biomes into tree-dominated areas⁶⁸. Higher C₃ assimilation under elevated [CO₂]_a al-
273 lows tree saplings to grow taller, increasing their probability to escape the fire trap⁶⁹. Higher car-
274 bon assimilation allows greater allocation to mechanical⁵⁶ and chemical³⁸ defences, and effective
275 cavitation repair. Further, reduced transpiration translates into water savings at the ecosystem
276 level⁷⁰, and may reduce flammability. These factors all drive the thickening of savannas^{40,49,71},
277 which is predicted to continue under future climatic scenarios⁶⁸. In the understory of progres-
278 sively closing ecosystems, shade tolerant saplings like *C. africana* will have an advantage and
279 could be preferentially recruited. Growing forest trees would eventually outshade savanna trees⁷²
280 transitioning back to closed, less flammable, tropical forest⁷³.

281

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287 Author contributions

288 DJB, CB and JQ designed the research. CB and JQ performed the research. NU, CB and JQ
289 analysed and presented the data. CB, JQ and NU wrote the paper with contributions from DJB.

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Figures

Figure 1. Canopy evapotranspiration and relative water content. Canopy evapotranspiration (E_{plant}) (top panels), and relative leaf water content (RWC, bottom panels) in response to watering levels and for three levels of growth [CO_2]_a in the forest broad-leaf tree *Celtis africana* (left), the savanna tree *Vachellia karroo* (centre), and the C₄ savanna grass *Eragrostis curvula* (right). Plants were grown in controlled-environment chambers at 200 ppm (Sub), 400 ppm (Amb) or 800 ppm (Ele) [CO_2]_a and they were subjected to progressive month-long decreasing watering levels of 80, 60, 50, 40, and, 30% of pot capacity followed by re-watering back to 80% (indicated by different shades of grey). Values are means \pm SE ($n = 4$). Horizontal differences (across watering levels within a given [CO_2]_a, not across CO_2 levels, $P < 0.05$) are indicated by different letters. Within waterings, differences between subambient and elevated are indicated with §; between subambient and ambient with †, and between elevated and ambient with ‡ ($P < 0.05$). When symbols appear in the corner they apply to all waterings. Statistical details and P -values are given in SI Table S1.

Figure 2. Leaf and pre-dawn water potential. Leaf water potential at midday (top) and predawn (a proxy for soil water potential, bottom) in response to decreasing levels of water supply and for three levels of growth $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ in *Celtis africana* (left), *Vachellia karroo* (centre), and *Eragrostis curvula* (right). Plants were grown in controlled-environment chambers at 200 ppm (Sub), 400 ppm (Amb) or 800 ppm (Ele) $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ and they were subjected to progressive month-long decreasing watering levels of 80, 60, 50, 40, and, 30% of pot capacity followed by re-watering back to 80% (shades of grey). Values are means \pm SE ($n=4$). Letters indicate horizontal significant differences ($P < 0.05$) across watering levels within a given $[\text{CO}_2]_a$, not across CO_2 levels. Symbols indicate differences ($P < 0.05$) between subambient and elevated (§), subambient and ambient (†) or elevated and ambient (‡); when shown in the corner they apply to all waterings. Statistical details and P -values are given in SI Table S1.

Figure 3. Leaf-level gas exchange under operational growth conditions. Stomatal conductance, g_s (top) and CO_2 assimilation, A_{op} (bottom), in response to decreasing levels of water supply and for three levels of growth $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ in *Celtis africana* (left), *Vachellia karroo* (centre), and *Eragrostis curvula* (right). Plants were grown in controlled-environment chambers at 200 ppm (Sub), 400 ppm (Amb) or 800 ppm (Ele) $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ and they were subjected to progressive month-long decreasing watering levels of 80, 60, 50, 40, and, 30% of pot capacity followed by re-watering back to 80% (shades of grey). Values are means \pm SE ($n=4$). Different letters indicate horizontal significant differences ($P < 0.05$) across watering levels within a given $[\text{CO}_2]_a$, not across CO_2 levels. Symbols indicate differences ($P < 0.05$) between subambient and elevated (§), subambient and ambient (†) or elevated and ambient (§); when shown in the corner they apply to all waterings. Statistical details and P -values are given in SI Table S1.

Figure 4. Photosynthetic parameters derived from *A-PPFD* response curves for *Celtis africana* (left), *Vachellia karroo* (centre) and *Eragrostis curvula* (right) grown at $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ of 200 ppm (circles and solid line), 400 ppm (squares and dashed line) and 800 ppm (triangles and dotted line). Photosynthetic responses to light intensity (*A-PPFD* curves, Figure S3) were measured at the growth $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ on randomly selected plants during each month-long water level interval and were used to derive the following parameters: respiration in the light (R_{LIGHT} , the *y*-intercept of an hyperbola fitted to *A-PPFD* curves); initial quantum yield for CO_2 fixation ($Y(\text{CO}_2)_{\text{LL}}$, the initial slope); light saturated gross assimilation rate (GA_{SAT} , the asymptote); and, the light compensation point (LCP , the *y*-intercept, i.e. *PPFD* when $GA = R_{\text{LIGHT}}$). Values are means ($n = 4$) \pm SE. Letters indicate horizontal significant differences ($P < 0.05$) across watering levels within a given $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ of 200 (black font), 400 (grey italic font) or 800 ppm (light grey font). If differences apply to all $[\text{CO}_2]_a$ only one set of letters are displayed. Symbols indicate vertical differences ($P < 0.05$) between subambient and elevated (§), subambient and ambient (†) or elevated and ambient (‡); when shown at the left they apply to all waterings. Statistical details and *P*-values are given in SI Table S1.

Figure 5. Photosynthetic parameters derived from A-C_i response curves for *Celtis africana* (left), *Vachellia karroo* (centre) and *Eragrostis curvula* (right) grown at [CO₂]_a of 200 ppm (circles and solid line), 400 ppm (squares and dashed line) and 800 ppm (triangles and dotted line). The A-C_i curves (Figure S4) were measured on randomly selected plants during each month-long water level and were used to derive the following parameters: carboxylation efficiency (CE, the initial slope of a fitted hyperbola); the maximal rubisco carboxylation rate (V_{C_{MAX}}) for C₃ trees, and maximal PEP carboxylation rate (V_{P_{MAX}}) for the C₄ grass that were mechanistically derived; CO₂ compensation point (Γ, the y-intercept, i.e. C_i when A = 0); CO₂-saturated assimilation rate (A_{SAT}, the asymptote, reflecting the potential for electron transport). Values are mean (n = 4) ± SE. Letters indicate significant differences (P < 0.05) across watering levels and apply to all [CO₂]_a. Symbols indicate vertical differences (P < 0.05) between subambient and elevated (§), subambient and ambient (†) or elevated and ambient (‡); when shown at the left they apply to all waterings. Statistical details and P-values are given in SI Table S1.

Figure 6. Starch content per dry weight in leaves (top) and roots (bottom) in response to decreasing levels of water supply and for three levels of growth [CO₂]_a in *Celtis africana* (left), *Vachellia karroo* (centre), and *Eragrostis curvula* (right). Plants were grown in controlled-environment chambers at 200 ppm (Sub), 400 ppm (Amb) or 800 ppm (Ele) [CO₂]_a and they were subjected to progressive month-long decreasing watering levels of 80, 60, 50, 40, and, 30% of pot capacity followed by re-watering back to 80% (shades of grey). Values are means ± SE (*n* = 4). Letters indicate significant differences (*P* < 0.05) across watering levels within a given [CO₂]_a, not across CO₂ levels. Symbols indicate differences (*P* < 0.05) between subambient and elevated (§), subambient and ambient (†) or elevated and ambient (‡); when shown in the corner they apply to all waterings. Statistical details and *P*-values are given in SI Table S1.

Table 1. Effects of [CO₂]_a over seasonal drought. Ln transformed g_s (operational stomata conductance), A_{op} (operational photosynthetic rate), leaf starch content, root starch content, midday and predawn leaf water potential (Ψ_{leaf} , Ψ_{pd}), and indicators of leaf photosynthetic capacity, which are R_{LIGHT} (respiration rate in the light), $Y(CO_2)_{LL}$ (initial quantum yield for CO₂ fixation), GA_{SAT} (light saturated gross assimilation rate), LCP (light compensation point), CE (carboxylation efficiency), V_{CMAX} : (maximal rubisco carboxylation rate, for the trees), V_{PMAX} (maximal PEP carboxylation rate, for the grass), Γ (CO₂ compensation point), and $ASAT$ (CO₂-saturated assimilation rate). The natural logarithm of variables over 80%, 60%, 50% and 40% watering were subjected to a generalised mixed linear model (REML, Genstat 18.2, VSNi, Hemel Hempstead, UK) with the effect of species nested within the life form (tree vs grass), [CO₂]_a and their interaction as fixed factors, plant, watering level and their interaction as random factors. The effect of [CO₂]_a was calculated as $lnv_t - lnv_{amb}$, where v_t and v_{amb} are the predicted estimates of any generic variable v under either high or low [CO₂]_a, and ambient [CO₂]_a, respectively (recall that $dlnv = \frac{dv}{v}$). The effect is dimensionless and can be directly compared across species and variables. Three scenarios were statistically tested: (H₁) the effect of [CO₂]_a is the same in trees and the C₄ grass *E. curvula*; (H₂) the effect of [CO₂]_a is the same in the trees *C. africana* and *V. karroo*, and the effect of [CO₂]_a is the same in the savanna species *E. curvula* and *V. karroo*.

	Mean under Amb CO ₂			Effect of Low CO ₂						Effect of High CO ₂					
	<i>Celtis africana</i>	<i>Vachellia karroo</i>	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	<i>Celtis africana</i>	<i>Vachellia karroo</i>	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	<i>p(trees = E. curvula)</i>	<i>p(C. africana = V. karroo)</i>	<i>p(E. curvula = V. karroo)</i>	<i>Celtis africana</i>	<i>Vachellia karroo</i>	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	<i>p(trees = E. curvula)</i>	<i>p(C. africana = V. karroo)</i>	<i>p(E. curvula = V. karroo)</i>
<i>Ln g_s</i>	-3.12	-2.66	-2.75	0.10	-0.48	0.64	0.002	0.026	0.003	-0.51	-0.37	-0.23	0.35	0.60	0.61
<i>Ln A_{op}</i>	1.38	1.36	2.12	-1.24	-0.68	0.12	<0.001	0.041	<0.001	0.14	0.80	0.21	0.14	<0.001	<0.001
<i>Ln Lf starch con.</i>	2.47	1.02	3.97	-1.01	-0.86	0.04	0.023	0.74	0.01	0.06	0.55	0.07	0.57	0.32	0.15
<i>Ln Rt starch con.</i>	1.79	1.50	1.55	-0.28	0.21	-0.17	-	-	0.28	0.01	0.04	-0.19	0.56	0.95	0.57
<i>Ln R_{LIGHT}</i>	-0.81	-0.60	0.29	-0.33	-0.43	-0.10	0.21	0.72	0.29	0.44	0.40	0.11	-	-	0.84
<i>Ln Y(CO₂)_{LL}</i>	-3.52	-3.69	-2.99	-0.13	-0.65	0.00	0.19	0.12	0.03	0.08	0.47	-0.02	0.28	0.24	0.13
<i>Ln GA_{SAT}</i>	1.39	2.19	2.83	-0.86	-1.20	-0.10	0.007	0.34	<0.001	0.16	0.76	0.15	0.16	0.034	0.004
<i>Ln LCP</i>	2.79	2.56	3.36	-0.42	0.58	-0.16	0.38	<0.001	0.02	0.05	0.06	0.00	0.84	0.96	1.00
<i>Ln CE</i>	-4.04	-2.75	-1.39	-0.38	-0.37	0.18	0.10	0.99	0.05	0.00	0.06	-0.15	0.47	0.83	0.44
<i>Ln V_{MAX}</i>	2.48	4.09	3.30	-0.26	-0.33	0.26	0.08	0.85	0.01	0.04	0.00	-0.03	0.81	0.88	0.85
<i>Ln Γ</i>	3.86	4.13	1.40	0.09	-0.02	-1.16	0.001	0.76	-	-0.02	-0.12	-0.29	0.42	0.77	0.66
<i>Ln ASAT</i>	2.08	2.89	2.61	-0.30	-0.39	0.11	0.11	0.78	0.002	0.12	0.10	0.17	0.76	0.92	0.30
<i>Ln Ψ_{pd}</i>	0.37	0.92	0.44	0.04	0.13	0.02	0.64	0.49	0.49	-0.03	-0.04	-0.09	0.70	0.95	0.78
<i>Ln Ψ_{leaf}</i>	0.56	1.11	0.70	0.19	0.22	0.11	0.19	0.68	0.18	-0.04	-0.07	-0.17	0.23	0.75	0.31

Physiological responses to low CO₂ over seasonal drought as drivers for forest-grassland transitions

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Methods

Plants and growth conditions

Seedlings of *Vachellia karroo*, obtained from the Desert Legume Program, (Tucson, AZ, US), accession number 900474 collected outside the Mountain Zebra National Park, Northwest of Cradock (Eastern Cape, ZA), *Celtis africana* from Silverhill Seeds (Cape Town, ZA) and a clone of *Eragrostis curvula* obtained from the Germplasm Resources Information Network (United States Department of Agriculture, Washington D.C., US), accession number PI-155434, were grown as described by Quirk, et al. ⁷⁴ in 2.5 dm³ pots filled with a loam soil that has a gradual decline in soil water potential when dried (Figure S2). Plants were randomly distributed between six controlled-environment growth chambers at duplicated [CO₂]_a levels of 200, 400, or 800 ppm, rotated weekly within, and monthly between, cabinets. Temperature was set at 26:17 °C and relative humidity was 70:50 % (day:night).

Trees and grasses were initially grown for 18 and 6 months, respectively, while watered to a gravimetrically determined 80% of pot capacity three times per week. Subsequently, during the experimental phase, all plants were watered for four-week periods to each 80%, 60%, 50%, 40% and 30% of pot capacity, followed by re-watering at 80%. The oldest leaves of *E. curvula* (about a third at the beginning, reducing to zero as drought progressed) were clipped every two to three weeks to maintain the initial canopy size.

Leaf and root starch concentration

During the experimental phase leaves and roots were collected from each plant every two weeks. Roots were extracted from two 2 cm diameter soil cores taken to a depth of 8 cm avoiding the main tap root of the trees. A total of 432 samples were microwaved, dried and ground in a mixer mill as described by Quirk, et al. ⁷⁵. Starch concentration was analysed with a highly specific enzymatic method optimised for plant samples ⁷⁶ that avoids errors of acid hydrolysis methods ⁷⁷. An internal reference comprised of a mix of roots and leaves of all species was analysed in parallel with $n = 6$ ⁷⁶ to quantify day drift, but the effect was not significant.

Leaf gas exchange and fluorometry

Instantaneous leaf gas exchange was measured on fully expanded leaves at midday, after ~12 photoperiod hours since watering, with an infra-red gas analyser fitted with a 6 cm² cuvette and a red-blue LED light source (LI6400XT fitted with 6400-02B, LI-COR

Biosciences, Lincoln, NE, US). For *E. curvula*, three to four leaf blades were aligned, avoiding gaps and overlaps, to fill the entire leaf chamber. For the other two species, whenever leaves did not fill the chamber, leaf area was measured using scaled digital images processed in ImageJ (NIH, Bethesda, MA, US) (Figure S1). To minimise environmental perturbations and error arising from CO₂ leakage from the IRGA, the leaf chamber was positioned inside the growth cabinet, and supplied with air from within the cabinet at [CO₂] of 200, 400 or 800 ppm, depending on growth conditions. Flow rate was 235 μmol s⁻¹, and PPFD and temperature were set to match growth conditions. After readings stabilised, gas exchange was averaged for 10 s and recorded as a single point measurement, to total 222 data points. The same leaves were used for measurements of chlorophyll fluorescence on dark adapted leaves (F_V/F_M) at least four hours after the end of the photoperiod using a Junior PAM (Heinz Walz GmbH, Effeltrich, DE) and factory settings.

Responses of net leaf CO₂ assimilation (A) to [CO₂] in the sub-stomatal cavity (C_i) and to PPFD ($A-C_i$ and $A-PPFD$ response curves) were measured as described by Bellasio, et al. ⁷⁸. Measurements were taken at the bench for each watering interval ($n = 4$, ~160 A -response curves) on the same (trees) or similar (grasses) leaves to those used for in-cabinet point measurements, between 3 and 72 hours after watering (for a schematic representation of the measurement and sampling strategy see Supporting Information in ⁷⁵). For $A-PPFD$ curves, reference [CO₂] was set to 200, 400 or 800 ppm, according to experimental treatment with ten PPFD increments between 1500 and zero μmol m⁻² s⁻¹, with 5–7 min between increments. For $A-C_i$ curves, PPFD was 1500 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹, and reference [CO₂] was incremented between 20 and 1200 ppm, with 2–3 min between increments. These curves were used to derive a series of enzyme- and light-limited photosynthetic parameters following Bellasio, et al. ⁷⁹ for *E. curvula* and Bellasio, et al. ⁸⁰ for the trees.

Plant–water relations

Canopy evapotranspiration (E_{plant}) was calculated from ~700 gravimetric measurements. Stomata conductance (g_s) was taken from the instantaneous gas exchange measurements described previously. Leaf water potential at midday (Ψ_{leaf}) and pre-dawn (Ψ_{pd}) were measured in 469 samples using a Scholander pressure chamber (PMS Instrument Company, Model 1000, Albany, OR, US) on leaves cut the day or night following instantaneous gas exchange after Fini, et al. ⁸¹. Relative water content was calculated for 238 samples as:
$$RWC = 100 \frac{\text{sample weight} - \text{dry weight}}{\text{turgid weight} - \text{dry weight}}$$
 Turgidity was achieved by submerging cut leaves in distilled water within a sealed environment for 3–4 h (Ghannoum, et al. ⁸²). Leaves were then oven-dried for 48 h at 60 °C.

Statistical analysis

The effect of drought and [CO₂]_a in individual species was analysed with a repeated generalized mixed linear model in SAS (v.9.4; SAS Institute, Cary, NC, USA). Modelled main effects were watering level, [CO₂]_a and their interaction; plant number was the random effect. Details and *P* values are presented in Table S1. Contrasts were performed with Fisher's PLSD differences and deemed significant at *P* < 0.05.

To test the effect of [CO₂]_a across species and over the seasonal drought, the natural logarithm of variables were subjected to a generalized mixed linear model (REML, Genstat 18.2, VSNi, Hemel Hempstead, UK, see Table S2). [CO₂]_a and species nested within the life form (trees vs grass) with their interaction were fixed factors, while plant and watering level with their interaction were random factors.

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Table S1. Within species effects of [CO₂]_a and watering level on leaf water relations, instantaneous gas exchange, indicators of leaf photosynthetic capacity, and starch content. Leaf water relations parameters: E_{plant} (canopy evapotranspiration), RWC (leaf relative water content), Ψ_{leaf} (midday leaf water potential), and Ψ_{pd} (predawn leaf water potential). Instantaneous gas exchange parameters: g_s (operational stomata conductance), and A_{op} (operational photosynthetic rate). Indicators of leaf photosynthetic capacity: R_{LIGHT} (respiration rate in the light), initial quantum yield for CO₂ fixation ($Y(\text{CO}_2)_{\text{LL}}$), light saturated gross assimilation rate (GA_{SAT}), light compensation point (LCP), carboxylation efficiency (CE), maximal rubisco carboxylation rate (V_{CMAX}), maximal PEP carboxylation rate (V_{PMAX}), CO₂ compensation point (Γ), and CO₂-saturated assimilation rate (AS_{AT}). Starch content: leaf starch concentration, and root starch concentration. Output from repeated-measures ANOVA in SAS (v.9.4; SAS Institute, Cary, NC, USA). Modelled main effects were [CO₂]_a, (200 ppm, 400 ppm or 800 ppm), watering level (WL: 80%, 60%, 50%, 40%, 30%, recovery), and their interaction; individual plant was the random effect. Analyses were: PROC MIXED (linear model) for normal data with homogenous variance; PROC GLIMMIX (generalized linear mixed model, dist = gaussian, logit identity) for normal data with heteroscedasticity; and PROC GLIMMIX (dist = gamma, logit link) for non normal data (absolute values were used in the case of variables with negative values). In all analysis individual comparisons for significant model effects were performed with Fisher's PLSD differences (LSMEANS or ILINK option of the LSMEANS statement in GLIMMIX). The table shows the F -statistic with numerator and denominator degrees of freedom and P -values. Bold font: significant effect $P < 0.05$. Numbers in cells represent: first number is Fndf,ddf: F value, numerator degrees of freedom, denominator degrees of freedom. Second number is P -value

	<i>Celtis africana</i>			<i>Vachellia karroo</i>			<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>					
	Analysis	CO ₂	WL	CO ₂ × WL	Analysis	CO ₂	WL	CO ₂ × WL	Analysis	CO ₂	WL	CO ₂ × WL
E_{plant}	Mixed	2.75 _{2, 12.2} 0.1036	133.17 _{5, 59.4} <0.0001	1.20 _{10, 59.4} 0.3110	Glimmix/ Gamma	1.81 _{2, 9.64} 0.2151	647.64 _{5, 35.92} <0.0001	1.46 _{10, 23.61} 0.2152	Mixed	156.82 _{2, 14.8} <0.0001	1256.72 _{5, 42.4} <0.0001	10.71 _{10, 42.8} <0.0001
RWC	Glimmix/ Gamma	8.64 _{2, 9.30} 0.0076	10.14 _{5, 38.84} <0.0001	4.43 _{10, 31.35} 0.0006	Mixed	1.52 _{2, 18.9} 0.2451	6.12 _{5, 42.7} 0.0002	1.63 _{10, 43.2} 0.1305	Glimmix/ Gamma	6.45 _{2, 54} 0.0031	133.58 _{5, 54} <0.0001	2.64 _{10, 54} 0.0107
Ψ_{leaf}	Glimmix/ Gamma	28.43 _{2, 47.44} <0.0001	32.25 _{5, 68.96} <0.0001	1.92 _{10, 47.69} 0.0651	Mixed	8.96 _{2, 12.8} 0.0037	344.01 _{5, 44} <0.0001	1.51 _{10, 43.9} 0.1693	Mixed	12.96 _{2, 19.8} <0.0003	384.55 _{5, 44} <0.0001	5.20 _{10, 44.4} <0.0001
Ψ_{pd}	Glimmix/ Gamma	17.22 _{2, 17.45} <0.0001	63.80 _{5, 39.81} <0.0001	3.37 _{10, 26.11} 0.0061	Mixed	4.52 _{2, 14.7} 0.0294	163.74 _{5, 43.5} <0.0001	1.31 _{10, 43.6} 0.2547	Glimmix/ Gamma	1.71 _{2, 5.33} 0.2664	298.61 _{5, 10.93} <0.0001	6.55 _{10, 11.66} 0.0018
g_s	Glimmix/ Gaussian	3.29 _{2, 4.19} 0.1384	1.72 _{5, 18.23} 0.1797	4.62 _{10, 15.67} 0.0036	Glimmix/ Gamma	6.21 _{2, 14.01} 0.0117	80.21 _{5, 32.63} <0.0001	3.68 _{10, 25.36} 0.0038	Glimmix/ Gamma	310.66 _{2, 12.26} <0.0001	4153.86 _{5, 25.2} <0.0001	15.70 _{10, 20.7} <0.0001
A_{op}	Glimmix/ Gaussian	27.25 _{2, 8.42} 0.0002	20.16 _{5, 26.2} <0.0001	7.53 _{10, 19.72} <0.0001	Glimmix/ Gamma	60.64 _{2, 16.61} <0.0001	105.57 _{5, 32.95} <0.0001	3.80 _{10, 27.76} 0.0026	Glimmix/ Gamma	8.20 _{2, 9.93} 0.0079	6911.76 _{5, 26.86} <0.0001	2.61 _{10, 24.29} 0.0259
R_{LIGHT}	Glimmix/ Gaussian	11.69 _{2, 8.84} 0.0033	15.20 _{4, 27.85} <0.0001	1.29 _{8, 20.85} 0.3034	Glimmix/ Gaussian	6.15 _{2, 7.91} 0.0244	0.51 _{5, 19.75} 0.7667	0.37 _{10, 18.45} 0.9441	Glimmix/ Gamma	1.10 _{2, 4.76} 0.4063	1.74 _{4, 22.41} 0.1766	0.44 _{8, 18.34} 0.8794
$Y(\text{CO}_2)_{\text{LL}}$	Glimmix/ Gaussian	1.49 _{2, 3.85} 0.3324	2.01 _{4, 17.6} 0.1372	1.84 _{8, 16.69} 0.1404	Glimmix/ Gaussian	28.60 _{2, 16.17} <0.0001	19.18 _{4, 19.71} <0.0001	0.87 _{8, 16.17} 0.5610	Mixed	0.32 _{2, 20.6} 0.7303	4.55 _{4, 33} 0.0049	0.82 _{8, 33.2} 0.5940
GA_{SAT}	Mixed	23.18 _{2, 16.8} <0.0001	5.23 _{4, 28.7} 0.0027	2.19 _{8, 28.6} 0.0587	Glimmix/ Gamma	152.77 _{2, 8.61} <0.0001	148.63 _{5, 21.87} <0.0001	35.60 _{10, 18.38} <0.0001	Glimmix/ Gaussian	3.67 _{2, 12.01} 0.0570	17.70 _{4, 32.26} <0.0001	1.02 _{8, 22.95} 0.4512
LCP	Glimmix/ Gamma	0.43 _{2, 6.48} 0.67	4.42 _{4, 12.45} 0.019	1.17 _{8, 11.78} 0.3881	Mixed	6.29 _{2, 14.1} 0.0112	8.41 _{5, 24.1} <0.0001	2.37 _{9, 23.6} 0.0452	Glimmix/ Gaussian	1.93 _{2, 8.882} 0.2019	8.19 _{4, 25.39} 0.0002	0.48 _{8, 20.63} 0.8533
CE	Glimmix/ Gaussian	2.68 _{2, 16.38} 0.0986	10.37 _{4, 1} 0.2284	3.31 _{8, 1} 0.4025	Glimmix/ Gamma	5.37 _{2, 6.234} 0.0441	55.27 _{5, 21.57} <0.0001	2.27 _{10, 15.75} 0.0705	Glimmix/ Gaussian	8.15 _{2, 8.23} 0.0112	8.54 _{4, 16.17} 0.0007	0.61 _{8, 12.42} 0.7509
V_{CMAX}	Glimmix/ Gaussian	2.49 _{2, 7.71} 0.1462	10.24 _{4, 18.8} <0.0001	1.98 _{8, 21.92} 0.0978	Glimmix/ Gamma	0.93 _{2, 11.28} 0.4216	46.22 _{5, 20.98} <0.0001	1.95 _{10, 16.14} 0.1118	-	-	-	-
V_{PMAX}	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Glimmix/ Gamma	6.76 _{2, 10.89} 0.0123	8.34 _{4, 23.75} 0.0002	0.52 _{8, 17.4} 0.8239
Γ	Mixed	0.03 _{2, 16.4} 0.9710	0.94 _{4, 32.2} 0.4517	0.74 _{8, 31.9} 0.6508	Glimmix/ Gamma	1.04 _{2, 13.25} 0.3812	30.13 _{5, 24.86} <0.0001	1.99 _{10, 22.12} 0.0857	Glimmix/ Gaussian	15.67 _{2, 16.88} 0.0001	1.28 _{4, 21.82} 0.3076	1.88 _{8, 19.94} 0.1211
AS_{AT}	Glimmix/ Gaussian	0.94 _{2, 6.109} 0.4419	7.00 _{4, 18.98} 0.0012	1.49 _{8, 12.67} 0.2540	Glimmix/ Gaussian	9.33 _{2, 10.42} 0.0048	14.43 _{5, 18.52} <0.0001	1.52 _{10, 16.21} 0.2173	Glimmix/ Gaussian	2.61 _{2, 11.73} 0.1154	17.00 _{4, 26.98} <0.0001	0.43 _{8, 18.62} 0.8910
Leaf starch	Glimmix/ Gamma	72.52 _{2, 16.9} <0.0001	28.45 _{5, 29.8} <0.0001	4.14 _{10, 21.4} 0.0028	Glimmix/ Gamma	15.36 _{2, 4.43} 0.0102	48.11 _{5, 31.12} <0.0001	5.52 _{10, 22.48} 0.0004	Glimmix/ Gaussian	0.58 _{2, 10.76} 0.5774	9.36 _{5, 35.16} <0.0001	1.03 _{10, 26.2} 0.4481
Root starch	Glimmix/ Gaussian	0.43 _{2, 6.48} 0.0384	4.42 _{4, 12.45} 0.6475	1.17 _{8, 11.78} 0.9714	Glimmix/ Gaussian	1.18 _{2, 8.92} 0.3520	2.73 _{5, 28.3} 0.0393	0.15 _{10, 24.34} 0.9981	Glimmix/ Gamma	1.85 _{2, 14.97} 0.1918	2.17 _{5, 38.19} 0.0781	1.23 _{10, 20.65} 0.3299

Supporting Figures

Figure S1. Experiment in progress. **A)** Seedlings of *Celtis africana* and *Vachellia karroo* during the growth phase before measurements began. **B)** A seedling of *Vachellia karroo* being weighed to gravimetrically determine watering amount. **C)** Seedlings inside the double-door growth chambers during the night phase of the photoperiod. **D)** *Eragrostis curvula* growing in the growth chambers; this picture was also taken during the dark phase of the photoperiod. The tobacco plants in **C** and **D** were grown alongside experimental plants throughout the experiment and were regularly monitored for growth and morphological traits to ensure they were reproducing treatment expected differences. **E)** Example of *in-situ* leaf area measurement prior to operational gas exchange data collection. The leaf is clamped between a piece of white Perspex mounted on a white card background and it is placed at a fixed distance from the camera lens. Subsequently, images are processed in Image J to determine area as illustrated in **F**, which displays monochrome images of *Vachellia karroo* leaflets.

Figure S2. Soil water retention of various substrates. Substrates were loosely filled into pots identical to those used in the experiments, watered to field capacity and left to dry under normal growth cabinet conditions. Soil water potential was measured every 2–3 days using a psychrometer (Psypro with L-51 hygrometers, Wescor Inc., Logan, UT, US) calibrated with five standard NaCl solutions according to the manufacturer’s instructions. Soil samples were extracted from the centre of the pot at a depth of ~10 cm using a weighing spatula. Soil and John Innes No. 3 (green up-triangles) was selected as the experimental substrate because it had the steadiest decrease in soil matric potential as it dried. $\Psi_m = \Psi_e \cdot (\theta/\theta_s)^{-b}$, where Ψ_m is soil matric potential, $\Psi_e = 0.0101$ and $b = 3.01$ are the fitted parameters.

Figure S3. Response of leaf-level CO₂ assimilation (A) to increasing photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD), A - PPFD curves. Values are means \pm 1 SE ($n = 4$) for *Celtis africana* (top), *Vachellia karroo* (middle), and *C₄ Eragrostis curvula* (bottom) plants, measured at five watering levels (80, 60, 50, 40 and 30% of pot capacity) and grown at either 200 ppm (left), 400 ppm (centre) or 800 ppm (right) [CO₂]_a. Blue symbols with solid blue lines represent measurements after re-watering (recovery phase).

Figure S4. Response of CO₂ assimilation (A) to increasing [CO₂] in the sub-stomatal cavity (C_i), A - C_i curves. Values are means ± 1 SE (n = 4) for *Celtis africana* (top), *Vachellia karroo* (middle) and C₄ *Eragrostis curvula* (bottom) plants, measured at five watering levels (80, 60, 50, 40 and 30% of pot capacity) and grown at either 200 ppm (left), 400 ppm (centre) or 800 ppm (right) [CO₂]_a. Blue symbols with solid blue lines represent measurements after re-watering (recovery phase).

Figure S5. [CO₂] in the sub-stomatal cavity (*C_i*) and its ratio to [CO₂] in the measuring cuvette (*C_i/C_a*) under operational growing conditions. Values are means \pm 1 S.E (*n* = 4) for the forest broad-leaf tree *Celtis africana* (left), the savanna tree *Vachellia karroo* (centre), and the C₄ savanna grass *Eragrostis curvula* (right), measured at five watering levels (80, 60, 50, 40 and 30% of pot capacity followed by a recovery back to 80%) and grown at either 200 ppm (Low), 400 ppm (Amb) or 800 ppm (Ele) [CO₂]_a. Gas exchange was measured in-cabinet with gas-analyser set points for temperature, humidity, [CO₂]_a, and light intensity set at cabinet levels.

Figure S6. Photochemical integrity of photosystem II as indicated by F_v/F_M . Values are means (*n* = 4) \pm 1 SE for the forest broad-leaf tree *Celtis africana* (left), the savanna tree *Vachellia karroo* (middle), and the C₄ savanna grass *Eragrostis curvula* (right), measured at five watering levels (80, 60, 50, 40 and 30% of pot capacity) followed by a recovery back to 80% and grown at either 200 ppm (Low), 400 ppm (Amb) or 800 ppm (Ele) [CO₂]_a. F_v/F_M was measured from pulse-amplitude modulated (PAM) chlorophyll fluorometry within the cabinets in the dark.

